

PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIPS IN THE FAMILY

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Annotation: It is known from the history of socio-economic development of human society that the development of a child's personality is formed in the family. The family is a small part of society, and it is a very important source of education that is responsible for raising a comprehensively healthy, harmoniously developed generation.

Keywords: father, mother, relationship, family, human society.

INTRODUCTION

It would not be a mistake to call all members of the Uzbek family literate, educated, and under the influence of these opportunities, boys and girls will be educated, thoughtful, resourceful, business-minded, intelligent. They are growing up.

The upbringing of a child in the family is of dual importance, not only because parents are not satisfied with teaching their children moral, spiritual and spiritual knowledge, but also because of the peculiarities of upbringing, its features, its content and they will need to be aware of the latest information about the meaning .

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Parents who are able to bring up their children wisely will spend their lives in pleasure and relaxation, will always see in their children nobility, kindness, kindness, and their hearts will never feel the pain of injury; they do not feel remorse. The Uzbek proverb says: "When a wedding grows up, the horse rests (that is, the horse is saved from riding)."

The father, who is the mainstay of the family, tastes all the hardships of life and is embodied as a great person who is distinguished by his unwavering will, justice, and endurance in the trials of life.

The father is the head of the family, the guardian. After all, the father has a human responsibility to take care of every aspect of the family, to show family members only the right path.

In the family, the father sets an example for his children in all aspects of behavior, speech, culture of interaction, and most importantly, practicality, honesty, sincerity and objectivity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A child with a strong imagination receives his first upbringing in the family. Abdullah Avloni, a well-known Uzbek pedagogue, said in his book "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" about the first lessons of raising a child:

It is advisable to build the reputation of adults in the family not on the basis of intimidation, but on the basis of sincerity and mutual respect. Family unity, mutual understanding, dress code, work ethic, conversations about other people and their other qualities and attributes bring new symbols to the child's imagination.

Family upbringing plays an important role in the future development of the child, the child first builds the image of society in the family, the rights and duties of the future citizen, worldview and moral views are formed in the family, on this basis he develops physically and spiritually. For a child, a healthy socio-emotional environment in the family is a source of cultural, spiritual and moral values, traditions, socio-life experiences, skills and abilities.

It is refined in the process of family upbringing, the essence of upbringing is to prepare a person for life, and the content, direction, purpose and task of upbringing depend on the social relations of people.

According to this relationship, a person looks at life in some way, understands the world through his thinking and forms his attitude to it, is brought up in the spirit of certain moral criteria, because family upbringing is deeply rooted in the spiritual world, feelings and emotions of children.

The spiritual environment in the family is very important in the upbringing of children, and the lifestyle of family members often determines the mood, imagination and emotions of children. This means that the family has a responsibility to society to bring up a healthy, well-rounded person.

Everyone who is brought up in a family must have all the qualities that are mature in all aspects of human morality, science, faith, and so on.

Perfection means that a person is just, strives for truth and goodness, has a clear conscience, realizes his mistakes and tries to get rid of them. awakens from a flat, fulfills all good wishes.

Bringing up the young generation as a harmonious, healthy person who can feel the feeling of homeland, first of all, depends on the family and parents.

In order to instill in the younger generation a sense of confidence in the future, it is necessary to deeply study the spiritual and moral heritage of our ancestors, to direct their talents and abilities to great goals.

For example, the increase in material wealth in families, the misuse of it by parents and children, the consumption of life in some adolescents, the

dependence on subsistence, humiliation, selfishness, the tendency to gain wealth without work.

CONCLUSION

In short, there are national rules for raising children in the family, and parents should use them appropriately. If there is spiritual peace and harmony in the family, if family members take care of each other, if they can find a basis for the upbringing of children, such an environment will have a positive impact on the upbringing of children and they bring true happiness to their children, which will lead to development in our work, progress in our society.

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